

ON m -EXPANSIVE AND m -CONTRACTIVE TUPLE OF OPERATORS IN HILBERT SPACES

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ABSTRACT. In this paper we introduce and studied the concept of joint m -expansive and joint m -contractive tuples of commuting operators of a Hilbert space.

1. INTRODUCTION

In this paper \mathcal{H} will denote a infinite-dimensional Hilbert space on $\mathbb{K} = \mathbb{C}$ (the complex plane). \mathbb{N} is the set of positive integers and $\mathbb{Z}_+ = \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$. Let $\mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$ be the set of bounded linear operators from \mathcal{H} into itself. An operator $S \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$ we denote by $\mathcal{N}(S)$ and $\mathcal{R}(S)$ the null space and the range of S respectively. For $S \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$, we set

$$\theta_m(S) := \sum_{0 \leq j \leq m} (-1)^j \binom{m}{j} S^{*j} S^j. \quad (1.1)$$

J. Agler and M. Stankus introduced the class of m -isometry on Hilbert space [1, 2, 3]. An operator $S \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$ is said to be m -isometric operator for some integer $m \geq 1$ if it satisfies the operator equation $\theta_m(S) = 0$.

Notice that the defining property $\theta_m(S) = 0$ of an m -isometric operator is equivalently formulated that

$$\sum_{0 \leq k \leq m} (-1)^k \binom{m}{k} \|S^k x\|^2 = 0 \quad (\forall x \in \mathcal{H}).$$

The Concept of m -isometric operators on Hilbert and Banach spaces has attracted much attention of various authors (see [8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 17, 21, 22, 19]). A generalization of m -isometries to m -expansive and m -contractive operators on Hilbert spaces spaces has been presented by several authors. We refer the reader to [4, 5, 6, 7, 14, 15, 18, 20, 23] for recent articles about these subjects.

Definition 1.1. ([14]) An operator $S \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$ is said to be

- (i) m -expansive ($m \geq 1$) if $\theta_m(S) \leq 0$.

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- (ii) m -hyperexpansive ($m \geq 1$), if $\theta_k(S) \leq 0$ for $k = 1, 2, \dots, m$.
- (iii) Completely hyperexpansive if $\theta_m(S) \leq 0$ for all m .

Definition 1.2. ([15]) An operator $S \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})$ is said to be

- (i) m -contractive ($m \geq 1$) if $\theta_m(S) \geq 0$.
- (ii) m -hypercontractive ($m \geq 1$), if $\theta_k(S) \geq 0$ for $k = 1, 2, \dots, m$.
- (iii) Completely hypercontractive if $\theta_m(S) \geq 0$ for all m .

The study of tuple of commuting operators on Hilbert space has consider by many authors in the recent years. In [16] the authors introduced the concept of m -isomeric tuple of commuting operators as follows: Let $\mathbf{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_d) \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})^d$ be tuple of commuting operators. \mathbf{S} is said to be m -isometric tuple if

$$\sum_{0 \leq k \leq m} (-1)^k \left(\sum_{|\alpha|=k} \frac{k!}{\beta!} \mathbf{S}^{*\beta} \mathbf{S}^\beta \right) = 0,$$

where $\beta = (\beta_1, \dots, \beta_d) \in \mathbb{Z}_+^d$ and $\beta! = \beta_1! \cdots \beta_d!$.

2. MAIN RESULTS

In this section, we introduce and study the concepts on m -expansive and m -contractive tuples of operators on a Hilbert space.

Let $\mathbf{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_d) \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})^d$ and set

$$\Psi_l(\mathbf{S}) = \sum_{0 \leq k \leq l} (-1)^k \left(\sum_{|\alpha|=k} \frac{k!}{\beta!} \mathbf{S}^{*\beta} \mathbf{S}^\beta \right), \quad (2.1)$$

and

$$\mathbf{Q}_l(\mathbf{S}, x) := \langle \mathbf{S}x, x \rangle = \sum_{0 \leq k \leq l} (-1)^k \binom{m}{k} \left(\sum_{|\beta|=k} \frac{k!}{\beta!} \|\mathbf{S}^\beta x\|^2 \right). \quad (2.2)$$

Clearly,

$$\Psi_l(\mathbf{S}) \geq 0 \iff \mathbf{Q}_l(\mathbf{S}, x) \geq 0 \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{H},$$

and

$$\Psi_l(\mathbf{S}) \leq 0 \iff \mathbf{Q}_l(\mathbf{S}, x) \leq 0 \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{H},$$

Definition 2.1. Let $\mathbf{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_d) \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})^d$ be a commuting tuple of operators and $m \in \mathbb{N}$. We said that

- (1) \mathbf{S} is joint m -expansive if $\Psi_m(\mathbf{S}) \leq 0$ for some integer m .
- (2) \mathbf{S} is joint m -hyperexpansive tuple if $\Psi_k(\mathbf{S}) \leq 0$ for each $k = 1, 2, \dots, m$.
- (3) \mathbf{S} is joint completely hyperexpansive tuple if $\Psi_k(\mathbf{S}) \leq 0$ for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$.
- (4) \mathbf{S} is joint m -contractive if $\Psi_m(\mathbf{S}) \geq 0$ for some integer m .
- (5) \mathbf{S} is joint m -hypercontractive if $\Psi_k(\mathbf{S}) \geq 0$ for each $k = 1, 2, \dots, m$.
- (6) \mathbf{S} is joint completely hypercontractive if \mathbf{S} is joint k -contractive for all positive integer k .

When $d = 1$, Definition 2.1 coincides with Definition 1.1 and Definition 1.2.

Remark. Observe that

$$\langle \Psi_l(\mathbf{S})x, x \rangle = \sum_{0 \leq k \leq l} (-1)^k \left(\sum_{|\beta|=k} \frac{k!}{\beta!} \|\mathbf{S}^\beta x\|^2 \right), \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{H}.$$

Then ;

$$(1) \mathbf{S} \text{ is } m\text{-expansive tuple} \iff \sum_{0 \leq k \leq l} (-1)^k \left(\sum_{|\beta|=k} \frac{k!}{\beta!} \|\mathbf{S}^\beta x\|^2 \right) \leq 0, \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{H},$$

and

$$(2) \mathbf{S} \text{ is } m\text{-contractive tuple} \iff \sum_{0 \leq k \leq l} (-1)^k \left(\sum_{|\beta|=k} \frac{k!}{\beta!} \|\mathbf{S}^\beta x\|^2 \right) \geq 0, \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{H}$$

Remark. (i) Let $\mathbf{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_d) \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})^d$ be a commuting tuple of operators. Then \mathbf{S} is a joint expansive tuple if

$$\|x\|^2 \leq \sum_{1 \leq j \leq d} \|S_j x\|^2, \quad (\forall x \in \mathcal{H}) \quad (2.3)$$

and it is a joint -contractive tuple if

$$\|x\|^2 \geq \sum_{1 \leq j \leq d} \|S_j x\|^2, \quad (\forall x \in \mathcal{X}). \quad (2.4)$$

(ii) If $d = 2$, let $\mathbf{S} = (S_1, S_2) \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})^2$ be a commuting pair of operators. Then \mathbf{S} is a joint 2-expansive pair if

$$\|x\|^2 \leq 2(\|S_1 x\|^2 + \|S_2 x\|^2) - (\|S_1^2 x\|^2 + \|S_2^2 x\|^2 + 2\|S_1 S_2 x\|^2) \quad (\forall x \in \mathcal{H}), \quad (2.5)$$

and it is a joint $(2, p)$ -contractive pair if

$$\|x\|^p \geq 2(\|S_1 x\|^2 + \|S_2 x\|^p) - (\|S_1^2 x\|^p + \|S_2^2 x\|^2 + 2\|S_1 S_2 x\|^2) \quad (\forall x \in \mathcal{H}). \quad (2.6)$$

(iii) Let $\mathbf{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_d) \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})^d$ be a commuting tuple of operators. Then \mathbf{S} is a joint 2-expansive tuple if

$$\|x\|^2 \leq 2 \sum_{1 \leq j \leq d} \|S_j x\|^2 - \left(\sum_{1 \leq j \leq d} \|S_j^2 x\|^2 + 2 \sum_{1 \leq j < k \leq d} \|S_j S_k x\|^2 \right) \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{H}, \quad (2.7)$$

and it is a joint 2-contractive tuple if

$$\|x\|^2 \geq 2 \sum_{1 \leq j \leq d} \|S_j x\|^2 - \left(\sum_{1 \leq j \leq d} \|S_j^2 x\|^p + 2 \sum_{1 \leq j \neq k \leq d} \|S_j S_k x\|^2 \right) \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{H}. \quad (2.8)$$

Remark. Since the operators S_1, \dots, S_d are commuting, every permutation of joint m -expansive tuple is also joint m -expansive tuple.

The following examples show that there exists a joint (m, p) -expansive (resp. joint (m, p) -contractive) operator which is not (m, p) -isometric tuple for some positive integer m .

Example 2.2. Let $\mathcal{H} = \mathbb{C}^3$ be equipped with the norm

$$\|(x, y, z)\|_2 = \left(|x|^2 + |y|^2 + |z|^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

and consider

$$S_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix} \in \mathcal{B}(\mathbb{C}^3) \text{ and } S_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \in \mathcal{B}(\mathbb{C}^3).$$

Then the pair $\mathbf{S} = (S_1, S_2)$ is a joint 2-expansive pair on $(\mathcal{H} = \mathbb{C}^3, \|\cdot\|_2)$.

In fact, obviously $S_1 S_2 = S_2 S_1$ and a simple computation shows that

$$\begin{aligned} & 2 \left\| S_1 \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{pmatrix} \right\|_2^2 + 2 \left\| S_2 \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{pmatrix} \right\|_2^2 - \left(\left\| S_1^2 \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{pmatrix} \right\|_2^2 + \left\| S_2^2 \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{pmatrix} \right\|_2^2 + 2 \left\| S_1 S_2 \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{pmatrix} \right\|_2^2 \right) \\ &= (9^2 - 1 + 3^2) |u + v + w|^2 \\ &\geq \left\| \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{pmatrix} \right\|_2^2. \end{aligned}$$

However \mathbf{S} is not a 2-isometric tuple.

Proposition 2.1. *Let $\mathbf{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_d) \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})^d$ be a tuple of commuting operators. Then for all positive integer m , and $x \in \mathcal{H}$, we have*

$$\mathbf{Q}_{m+1}(\mathbf{S}, x) = \mathbf{Q}_m(\mathbf{S}, x) - \sum_{1 \leq k \leq n} \mathbf{Q}_m(\mathbf{S}, S_k x). \quad (2.9)$$

Proof. By taking into account Equation (2.4), a straightforward calculation shows that

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbf{Q}_{m+1}(\mathbf{S}, x) \\ &= \sum_{0 \leq k \leq m+1} (-1)^k \binom{m+1}{k} \sum_{|\beta|=k} \frac{k!}{\beta!} \|\mathbf{S}^\beta x\|^2 \\ &= \|x\|^2 + \sum_{1 \leq k \leq m} (-1)^k \left[\binom{m}{k} + \binom{m}{k-1} \right] \sum_{|\beta|=k} \frac{k!}{\beta!} \|\mathbf{S}^\beta x\|^2 \\ &\quad + (-1)^{m+1} \sum_{|\beta|=m+1} \frac{(m+1)!}{\beta!} \|\mathbf{S}^\beta x\|^2 \\ &= \mathbf{Q}_m(\mathbf{S}, x) - \sum_{0 \leq k \leq m-1} (-1)^k \binom{m}{k} \sum_{|\beta|=k+1} \frac{(k+1)!}{\beta!} \|\mathbf{S}^\beta x\|^2 \\ &\quad + (-1)^{m+1} \sum_{|\beta|=m+1} \frac{(m+1)!}{\beta!} \|\mathbf{S}^\beta x\|^2 \\ &= \mathbf{Q}_m(\mathbf{S}, x) - \sum_{0 \leq k \leq m-1} (-1)^{m-k} \binom{m}{k} \sum_{|\beta|=k+1} \frac{k!(\beta_1 + \dots + \beta_n)}{\beta_1! \cdot \beta_2! \cdot \dots \cdot \beta_n!} \|\mathbf{S}^\beta x\|^2 \\ &\quad + (-1)^{m+1} \sum_{|\beta|=m+1} \frac{m!(\beta_1 + \dots + \beta_n)}{\beta_1! \cdot \beta_2! \cdot \dots \cdot \beta_n!} \|\mathbf{S}^\beta x\|^2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \mathbf{Q}_m(\mathbf{S}, x) \\
&\quad - \sum_{1 \leq j \leq n} \sum_{0 \leq k \leq m-1} (-1)^k \binom{m}{k} \sum_{|\beta|=k+1} \frac{k! \beta_j}{\beta_1! \cdot \beta_2! \cdots \beta_n!} \\
&\quad \cdot \|S_j (S_1^{\beta_1} \cdots S_j^{\beta_j-1} S_{j+1}^{\beta_{j+1}} \cdots S_n^{\beta_n} x)\|^2 \\
&\quad + (-1)^{m+1} \sum_{1 \leq j \leq d} \sum_{|\beta|=m+1} \frac{m! \beta_j}{\beta_1! \cdot \beta_2! \cdots \beta_d!} \\
&\quad \cdot \|S_j S_1^{\beta_1} \cdots S_j^{\beta_j-1} S_{j+1}^{\beta_{j+1}} \cdots S_n^{\beta_n} x\|^2 \\
&= \mathbf{Q}_m(\mathbf{S}, x) \\
&\quad - \sum_{1 \leq j \leq d} \sum_{0 \leq k \leq m-1} (-1)^k \binom{m}{k} \sum_{|\beta|=k} \frac{k!}{\beta!} \|\mathbf{S}^\alpha S_j x\|^2 \\
&\quad + (-1)^{m+1} \sum_{1 \leq j \leq d} \sum_{|\beta|=m} \frac{m!}{\beta!} \|\mathbf{S}^\alpha S_j x\|^2 \\
&= \mathbf{Q}_m(\mathbf{S}, x) - \sum_{1 \leq j \leq n} \left(\sum_{0 \leq k \leq m} (-1)^k \binom{m}{k} \sum_{|\beta|=k} \frac{k!}{\beta!} \|\mathbf{S}^\alpha S_j x\|^2 \right) \\
&= \mathbf{Q}_m(\mathbf{S}, x) - \sum_{1 \leq j \leq d} Q_m(\mathbf{S}; S_j x),
\end{aligned}$$

and so the equality (2.5) is satisfied. \square

Example 2.3. Let \mathcal{H} be an Hilbert space and $I_{\mathcal{H}}$ the identity operator. Then $(5I_{\mathcal{H}}, I_{\mathcal{H}}, I_{\mathcal{H}}) \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})^3$ is a joint 2-contractive of operators which is not a 2-isometric tuple..

It is well-known that the class of m -isometric tuple is a subset of the class of $(m+1)$ -isometric tuple. The following example shows that the class of joint m -expansive tuple and joint $m+1$ -expansive tuple are independent.

Example 2.4. Let $\mathbf{S} = (I_{\mathcal{H}}, I_{\mathcal{H}}, I_{\mathcal{H}}) \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})^3$. A simple computation shows that

- (1) \mathbf{S} is a joint 1-expansive tuple but not a joint 2-expansive tuple.
- (2) \mathbf{S} is a joint 2-contractive tuple but not a joint 1-contractive tuple.

The following theorem gives some sufficient conditions under which a joint m -expansive tuple of operators in Hilbert space is a joint m -hyperexpansive tuple for $m \geq 2$.

Theorem 2.2. Let $\mathbf{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_d) \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})^d$ be a commuting tuple of operators. If \mathbf{S} is a joint m -expansive tuple and satisfies the following conditions

- (1) $S_j^{k_j} \rightarrow 0$ strongly for all $j \in \{1, \dots, d\}$,
- (2) $S_j^* \Psi_k(\mathbf{S}) S_j \leq S_j^{*2} \Psi_k(\mathbf{S}) S_j^2$ for all $j \in \{1, \dots, d\}$ and $k \in \{1, \dots, m-1\}$,
then \mathbf{S} is a joint m -hyperexpansive tuple.

Proof. As \mathbf{S} is a joint m -expansive tuple, it follows that

$$\sum_{0 \leq k \leq m} (-1)^k \binom{m}{k} \left(\sum_{|\beta|=k} \frac{k!}{\beta!} \mathbf{S}^{*\beta} \mathbf{S}^\beta \right) \leq 0.$$

A computation shows that

$$\begin{aligned}
0 &\geq I_{\mathcal{H}} + \sum_{1 \leq k \leq m-1} (-1)^k \binom{m}{k} \left(\sum_{|\beta|=k} \frac{k!}{\beta!} \mathbf{S}^{*\beta} \mathbf{S}^\beta \right) + (-1)^m \sum_{|\beta|=m} \frac{m!}{\beta!} \mathbf{S}^{*\beta} \mathbf{S}^\beta \\
&= I_{\mathcal{H}} + \sum_{1 \leq k \leq m-1} (-1)^k \left(\binom{m-1}{k} + \binom{m-1}{k-1} \right) \sum_{|\alpha|=k} \frac{k!}{\alpha!} \mathbf{S}^{*\alpha} \mathbf{S}^\alpha + (-1)^m \sum_{|\beta|=m} \frac{m!}{\beta!} \mathbf{S}^{*\beta} \mathbf{S}^\beta \\
&= \underbrace{\sum_{0 \leq k \leq m-1} (-1)^k \binom{m-1}{k} \sum_{|\beta|=k} \frac{k!}{\beta!} \mathbf{S}^{*\beta} \mathbf{S}^\beta}_{\Psi_{m-1}(\mathbf{S})} - \sum_{0 \leq k \leq m-2} (-1)^k \binom{m-1}{k} \sum_{|\beta|=k+1} \frac{(k+1)!}{\beta!} \mathbf{S}^{*\beta} \mathbf{S}^\beta \\
&\quad + (-1)^m \sum_{|\beta|=m} \frac{m!}{\beta!} \mathbf{S}^{*\beta} \mathbf{S}^\beta
\end{aligned}$$

In view of the statement (2), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
\Psi_{m-1}(\mathbf{S}) &\leq \sum_{1 \leq j \leq d} S_j^* \left(\sum_{0 \leq k \leq m-1} (-1)^k \binom{m-1}{k} \sum_{|\beta|=k} \frac{k!}{\beta!} \mathbf{S}^{*\beta} \mathbf{S}^\beta \right) S_j \\
&= \sum_{1 \leq j \leq d} S_j^* \Psi_{m-1}(\mathbf{S}) S_j \\
&\leq \sum_{1 \leq j \leq d} S_j^{*2} \Psi_{m-1}(\mathbf{S}) S_j^2 \\
&\leq \dots \\
&\leq \sum_{1 \leq j \leq d} S_j^{*k_j} \Psi_{m-1}(\mathbf{S}) S_j^{k_j},
\end{aligned}$$

for every $k = (k_1, \dots, k_d) \in \mathbb{Z}_+^d$. By the assumption in the statement (1) it follows that $\Psi_{m-1}(\mathbf{S}) \leq 0$. Repeating the process as above we can prove that

$$\Psi_l(\mathbf{S}) \leq 0 \quad \forall l \in \{1, 2, \dots, m\}.$$

This yields the conclusion that the operator \mathbf{S} is a joint m -hyperexpansive tuple. \square

A similar argument to the one above proves the following theorem:

Theorem 2.3. *Let $\mathbf{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_d) \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})^d$ be a commuting tuple of operators. If \mathbf{S} is a joint m -contractive tuple and satisfies the following conditions*

- (1) $S_j^{k_j} \rightarrow 0$ strongly for all $j \in \{1, \dots, d\}$,
- (2) $S_j^* \Psi_k(\mathbf{S}) S_j \geq S_j^{*2} \Psi_k(\mathbf{S}) S_j^2$ for all $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, d\}$ and $k \in \{1, \dots, m-1\}$,
then \mathbf{T} is m -hypercontractive tuple.

Proposition 2.4. *Let $\mathbf{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_d) \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})^d$ be commuting tuple of operators such that $\mathbf{S}_{/\overline{\mathcal{R}(\mathbf{S})}} := (S_1/\overline{\mathcal{R}(\mathbf{S})}, \dots, S_d/\overline{\mathcal{R}(\mathbf{S})})$ is a joint 1-isometric tuple. The following properties hold.*

- (1) *If \mathbf{S} is joint m -expansive tuple, then \mathbf{S} is m -hyperexpansive tuple.*
- (2) *If \mathbf{S} is joint m -contractive tuple, then \mathbf{S} is a joint m -hypercontractive tuple.*

Proof. By (2.9) we have for all $k \in \{1, 2, \dots, m\}$

$$Q_k(\mathbf{S}, x) = \mathbf{Q}_{k-1}(\mathbf{S}, x) - \sum_{1 \leq j \leq d} \mathbf{Q}_{k-1}(\mathbf{S}, S_j x), \quad \forall x \in \mathcal{H}.$$

If \mathbf{S} is a joint isometric tuple on $\overline{\mathcal{R}(\mathbf{S})}$, it is well known that \mathbf{S} is an k -isometric tuple on $\overline{\mathcal{R}(\mathbf{S})}$ for $k = 1, \dots, m$. Consequently,

$$\mathbf{Q}_1(\mathbf{S}, x) = \mathbf{Q}_2(\mathbf{S}, x) = \dots = \mathbf{Q}_{m-1}(\mathbf{S}, x) = \mathbf{Q}_m(\mathbf{S}, x) = 0.$$

If \mathbf{S} is a joint m -expansive tuple, then it is a joint $(m-1)$ -expansive tuple. By repeating this process we get obtain that \mathbf{S} is joint k -expansive tuple for $k = 1, 2, \dots, m$. Consequently, \mathbf{S} is joint m -hyperexpansive.

By the same argument as above, (2) is obtained. \square

A point $\mu = (\mu_1, \dots, \mu_d) \in \mathbb{C}^d$ is said to be a joint approximate point of $\mathbf{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_d)$ if there exists a unit sequence of vectors $(\xi_n)_n \subset \mathcal{H}$ such that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|(S_j - \mu_j)\xi_n\| = 0 \quad \text{for } j = 1, \dots, d.$$

The joint approximate point spectrum of \mathbf{S} , denoted by $\sigma_{ap}(\mathbf{S})$ is defined by

$$\sigma_{ap}(\mathbf{S}) := \{\mu = (\mu_1, \dots, \mu_d) \in \mathbb{C}^d / \mu \text{ is a joint approximate point spectrum of } \mathbf{S}\}.$$

We denote by

$$\mathbb{B}(\mathbb{C}^d) := \{\mu = (\mu_1, \dots, \mu_d) \in \mathbb{C}^d / \|\mu\|_2 = \left(\sum_{1 \leq j \leq d} |\mu_j|^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} < 1\}$$

and

$$\partial\mathbb{B}(\mathbb{C}^d) := \{\mu = (\mu_1, \dots, \mu_d) \in \mathbb{C}^d / \|\mu\|_2 = \left(\sum_{1 \leq j \leq d} |\mu_j|^2 \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} = 1\}.$$

Proposition 2.5. *Let $\mathbf{S} = (S_1, \dots, S_d) \in \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{H})^d$ be an m -expansive tuple for some positive integer m . The following properties hold.*

(1) *If m is even, then the approximate point spectrum of \mathbf{S} lies in the boundary of the unit ball of $(\mathbb{C}^d, \|\cdot\|_2)$.*

(2) *If m is odd, then $\sigma_{ap}(\mathbf{S}) \subset \mathbb{C}^d \setminus \mathbb{B}(\mathbb{C}^d)$ and $\mathcal{N}(\mathbf{S}) := \bigcap_{1 \leq j \leq d} \mathcal{N}(S_j) = \{0\}$.*

Proof. Let $\mu = (\mu_1, \dots, \mu_d) \in \mathbb{C}^d$ is in the approximate point spectrum of \mathbf{S} , then there exists a sequence $(\xi_n)_n \subset \mathcal{X}$ such that for all n , $\|\xi_n\| = 1$ and $\|(S_j - \mu_j)\xi_n\| \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow +\infty$. Thus for each integer $\beta_j \in \mathbb{N}$, $\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \|(S_j^{\beta_j} - \mu_j^{\beta_j})\xi_n\| = 0$ and so that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \|(\mathbf{S}^\beta - \mu^\beta)\xi_n\| = 0 \quad \forall \beta = (\beta_1, \dots, \beta_d) \in \mathbb{Z}_+^d.$$

Now it is easy to see that

$$\|\mathbf{S}^\beta \xi_n\|^2 \longrightarrow |\mu|^{2\beta} \quad \text{as } n \longrightarrow \infty.$$

Since \mathbf{S} is an (m, p) -expansive, it follows that

$$0 \geq \sum_{0 \leq k \leq m} (-1)^k \binom{m}{k} \left(\sum_{|\alpha|=k} \frac{k!}{\alpha!} \|(\mathbf{S})^\alpha \xi_n\|^2 \right)$$

By taking $n \rightarrow \infty$ in the last inequality, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &\geq \sum_{0 \leq k \leq m} (-1)^k \binom{m}{k} \sum_{|\alpha|=k} \frac{k!}{\beta!} |\mu^\beta|^2 \\ &\geq \sum_{0 \leq k \leq m} (-1)^k \binom{m}{k} \sum_{|\beta|=k} \frac{k!}{\beta!} |\mu^\beta|^2 \\ &\geq (1 - \|\mu\|_2^2)^m. \end{aligned}$$

So,

$$(1 - \|\mu\|_p^p)^m \leq 0 \tag{2.10}$$

Now, we have that

(1) If m is even, then $0 \leq (1 - \|\mu\|_p^p)^m \leq 0$ from (2.10), and so $\|\mu\|_2 = 1$. This means that $\sigma_{ap}(\mathbf{S}) \subset \partial\mathbb{B}(\mathbb{C}^d)$ and so

$$\partial\sigma(\mathbf{S}) \subset \sigma_{ap}(\mathbf{S}) \subset \partial\mathbb{B}(\mathbb{C}^d).$$

(2) Assume that m is odd. If $\|\mu\|_2 < 1$, then $0 < (1 - \|\mu\|_2^2)^m \leq 0$ from (2.10), which is a contradiction. Hence,

$\sigma_{ap}(\mathbf{S}) \subset \mathbb{C}^d \setminus \mathbb{B}(\mathbb{C}^d)$. In particular $(0, \dots, 0) \notin \sigma_{ap}(\mathbf{S})$. Thus $\mathcal{N}(\mathbf{S}) = \{0\}$. \square

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